

POLYTECHNIQUE
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THERMAL AND STRUCTURAL PARAMETRIC STUDY OF THE SANDWICH PANEL STRUCTURE OF A THERMOPLASTIC 3D-PRINTED LUNAR ROVER

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Fonds de recherche
Nature et
technologies

Québec

NSERC
CRSNG

CREPEC

Centre de recherche
sur les systèmes polymères et
composites à haute performance

Lunar rover : Yutu 1

spaceflightnow.com

Multi-layer insulation (MLI)

bronaerotech.com

15 Earth's days

-180°C

Radioisotope thermoelectric generator (RTG)

wikipedia.com/Radioisotope_thermoelectric_generator

Most constraining mechanical load case

Random vibrations

- *Rocket thrust*
- *Liftoff*
- *Turbulences*
- *Motor burn*
- *POGO effect*

High performance thermoplastic

Low conductivity
 Mechanical properties
 Low density
 Space grade material

Composites

3D printing (FFF)

T. Osswald et al. (2018). Additive Manufacturing

Khechai et al. (2013). ResearchGate

Sandwich panel forming the base of the rover's structure :

- Critical structural part
- 3D-printed honeycomb core (PEEK 20% m CF)
- Laminate skins (PEEK w/ continuous carbon fibers)
- Fixed to the rocket module by a reinforcement ring
- Outside of the rover covered in **MLI**

Define recommendations to **reduce mass** of the sandwich panel while :

➤ Surviving the lunar nights **cold temperatures**

1. Thermal parametric study

➤ Resisting to the **random vibrations environnement**
of a rocket launch

2. Structural parametric study

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1. Thermal parametric study

2. Structural parametric study

Complete thermal panel

$$q'' = 4.1\bar{6} \text{ W/m}^2$$

Titanium ring
MLI

Radiation

$$T = -190^\circ\text{C}$$

Unit cell

$$q'' = 4.1\bar{6} \text{ W/m}^2$$

MLI

Radiation

$$T = -190^\circ\text{C}$$

Success criteria / Effective thermal resistance :

$$R_{eff} \geq 0,056 \text{ m}^2 \text{ K/W}$$

Finite element method

CORE'S WALL LENGTH

1. Thermal parametric study

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CORE'S WALL LENGTH

1. Thermal parametric study

CORE'S WALL THICKNESS

1. Thermal parametric study

To **increase thermal resistance** of the sandwich panel, we recommend to :

- t_c core's wall thickness
- t_s skin thickness
- h panel thickness
- ℓ $4\% < \rho^* < 8\%$
- S Regular hexagonal cells

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Success criteria / Effective thermal resistance :

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2. Structural parametric study

Complete structural panel

Simplified structural panel

NSM = 30 kg distributed across its surface

Failure criteria : Tsai-Hill < 1

Define recommendations to reduce mass of the sandwich panel while :

- Resisting to the **random vibrations environment** of a rocket launch

2. Structural parametric study

Output PSD (SOL 111)

Failure criteria : Tsai-Hill < 1

STRONGEST SPECIFIC PANEL MODELED

2. Structural parametric study

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2. Structural parametric study

FINAL RECOMMENDATIONS

To **reduce mass** of the sandwich panel forming the base of the lunar rover's frame :

Thermal

&

Structural

S Regular hexagonal cells

t_c core's wall thickness

t_s skin thickness

h panel thickness

ρ^* $4\% < \rho^* < 8\%$

h panel thickness

ℓ $7\text{ mm} < \ell < 11\text{ mm}$

- **Customed** thermoplastic rover structures
- **Optimisation** of the structure for a given loading case
- Study of the **in-plane conduction** impact of rover's structure

Duchesne O. (2021)

PEEK Sandwich Panel Lunar Rover Structure

Chila, M. (2021). ASC

